

Supplementary material to:

E.S. Medvedev and V.G. Ushakov, Irregular semi-empirical dipole-moment function for carbon monoxide and line lists for all its isotopologues verified for extremely high overtone transitions.

Band 2-0

Band 3-0

Band 4-0

Band 5-0

Fig. S1. The relative deviations of the calculated and measured line intensities, Eq. (8), for the principal isotopologue, %. The calculations are performed with the irregular, regular, and rational DMFs. The differences between the irregular and rational DMFs are indistinguishable in all bands. The difference between the irregular and regular DMFs manifest only in the 5-0 band (filled and empty circles, respectively).

Fig. S2. The same as in Fig. S1 for minor isotopologues.